

Evolving Paradigms in the Search for Advanced Extraterrestrial Intelligence

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Our nascent search for advanced extraterrestrial life is driven by humanity's anthropocentric tendencies. These tendencies much change to a more open-minded, multi-faceted, and scientifically rigorous approach to one of humanity's most profound questions: Are we alone in the universe? This question is addressed from both a deductive and inductive perspective. Science's approach to this question is changing, new paradigms will be needed, and an answer to this question may provide us with a new view of ourselves.

Keywords: extraterrestrial; UAP; UFO; Fermi paradox; ETH; space

Introduction

It is important to understand the history of the search for extraterrestrial intelligence (SETI) during the mid to late 20th century. There was a strong bias against the search for intelligent life beyond Earth. Resistance to SETI stemmed from several factors:

- (1) The possibility that life on Earth was unique. Many scientists believed the development of life in the cosmos required the coming together of many critical factors, which were unique to Earth. There were various views including: Earth had a highly unusual position in our solar system making it uniquely suitable for the development of life; there was no evidence that solar systems had formed around other stars; and if life existed elsewhere in the galaxy then it would have expanded to the Earth by now (Conway, 2003; Jones, 1981; Tipler, 1980; Ward & Brownlee, 2000).
- (2) Our inability to find life elsewhere. There was no known life in our solar system beyond the Earth. The search and identification of a planet with life in another star system was considered the equivalent of searching for the proverbial needle

in a haystack (Vaas et al., 1994; Ward & Brownlee, 2000). We were a pale blue dot in the cosmos and the ability to find another pale blue dot seemed remote.

- (3) The vast distances between the stars. The possibility of physical contact between extraterrestrial civilizations seemed impossible. Interstellar travel was considered a pipe dream. The nearest star was over four light years distant, and it would take our fastest spacecraft tens of thousands of years to reach it (Hart, 1975; Hoerner, 1962). The only hope of contact was considered to be through radio waves.

The idea of using radio waves to detect extraterrestrial intelligence (ET) emerged in the mid-20th century (Cocconi & Morrison, 1959). Shortly thereafter, the modern Search for Extraterrestrial Intelligence (SETI) began in 1960 with Frank Drake's Project Ozma, using a radio telescope in West Virginia. The receiver was tuned to the frequency of interstellar hydrogen, 1420 MHz (Drake, 1961). Based on the anthropocentric assumption that an alien intelligence would use radio waves for communication, we even focused our search on a specific frequency. This line of reasoning was taken one step further in the novel *Contact*; aliens from Vega pick up TV pictures of Hitler opening the 1936 Olympics (Sagan, 1985). These views were misplaced as today, long distance communication on Earth is primarily digital (Hart, 2010). We realize it is no longer reasonable to limit the electromagnetic bandwidths of potential extraterrestrial communications to those that are used on Earth (NASA, 2018).

Frank Drake, Carl Sagan, Jill Tartar, Cocconi & Morrison, and other SETI-oriented scientists were the open-minded leaders of their day in a world that thought the search for extraterrestrial intelligence sheer nonsense. NASA's foray into SETI in the late 1960s and early 1970s ended in disaster when in 1979 Senator William Proxmire awarded his "Golden Fleece" award to NASA's use of taxpayer dollars to search for

extraterrestrial civilizations. This contributed to the cancelation of congressional funding of NASA's SETI program in 1993 (Garber, 1999). Partly because of these impediments the private SETI Institute was formed in 1984 for the purpose of detecting radio signals. The SETI Institute took over the role that NASA once led and slowly grew through private donations. Today there are approximately 100 scientists working on projects at the SETI Institute. The frequencies examined have also expanded from optical wavelengths to microwaves (SETI, 2024). Nonetheless, there has been no confirmed detection of an electromagnetic (EM) signal from an ET civilization.

Deductive Analysis: The Case for the Extraterrestrial Hypothesis (ETH)

The ETH in this paper is defined as a hypothesis that advanced intelligence exists on some of the exoplanets around other stars and some of those ET civilizations may have sent space probes to Earth. The ETH is an attempt to answer one of humanity's most profound questions: Are we alone in the universe? This paper proposes that there are four key tenets when considering the extraterrestrial hypothesis (ETH):

- (1) Do advanced ET civilizations likely exist and is it likely that they are prevalent in our galaxy?
- (2) Would an advanced ET civilization be aware of Earth's existence?
- (3) Would an advanced ET civilization have an interest in communicating with us by sending probes to Earth?
- (4) Would an advanced ET civilization have the capability to send probes to Earth?

If the answer to all four of those components is positive, then we have a reasonable justification for examining near-Earth space for signs of ET probes.

ET Civilizations in our Galaxy

Is it likely that advanced ET civilizations are prevalent in our galaxy? Frank Drake first attempted to estimate the number of ET civilizations in our galaxy in 1961 with what has become known as the Drake equation:

$$N = R^* \cdot f_p \cdot n_e \cdot f_l \cdot f_i \cdot f_c \cdot L$$

where: N = number of civilizations in the galaxy that emit radio signals; R^* = rate of star formation in our galaxy; f_p = fraction of those stars with planetary systems; n_e = number of habitable planets in each planetary system; f_l = fraction of those planets that have developed life; f_i = fraction of those planets that have developed intelligent life; f_c = fraction of civilizations that perform interstellar communications; and L = length of time that these civilizations release detectable signals into space.

Two of the key parameters in this equation are f_p and n_e . f_p is an estimate of the fraction of stars with planets and n_e is an estimate of the fraction of stars with habitable planets (Drake, 1965). Both fractions were considered small in the 1960s as there was no established evidence for the existence of other solar systems or planets in a habitable zone for life as we know it to develop. It is easy to understand why there would not have been much interest in the search for ET based on the knowledge at the time.

The resistance to SETI began to change in 1992 and could be considered a paradigm shift in how we viewed ourselves in the cosmos. The first planet outside of our solar system was discovered (Wolszczan & Frail, 1992). By December 2009, there had been over 400 exoplanet planets confirmed, mostly by radial velocity (NASA, 2024). Radial velocity is a technique used to detect exoplanets by measuring changes in the motion of a star caused by the gravitational influence of an orbiting planet. Those methods are predisposed to detection of very large planets in the size range of Neptune to Jupiter or larger that orbit extremely close to their star. But none of these types of planets are thought to harbor life.

The ability to detect a smaller planet has improved as astrophysicists turned to the use of the transit method. This technique measures the decrease in light detected from a star when one of its planets transits between the star and Earth. The launch of the Kepler space telescope in March 2009 placed a platform in space that used the transit method of planet detection. Kepler's capability brought us close enough to be able to detect planets the size of Earth that orbit smaller M-class stars at a distance that could support life as we know it. By December 2016 analysis of data from the Kepler telescope had increased the number of confirmed exoplanets to 3444 (NASA, 2024). These numbers have improved with more Kepler findings and findings from terrestrial based telescopes. The launch of the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS) in 2018 has already begun to raise the number. With all these new efforts, "Candidates" have moved to the "Confirmed" category over the last few years so that by December 10, 2024, the number of confirmed exoplanets reached 5806 (NASA, 2024).

The Kepler Mission results show that most stars have planets, many of these planets are similar in size to the Earth, and systems with several planets are common (Borucki, 2016). Estimates of the number of earth-like planets in the habitable zone vary from approximately 1/3 to almost 90% of sun-like star systems (Bryson et al., 2021). Using this new information, the Drake equation's fractional values for f_p and n_e are close to 1. This would mean that there are about 125 billion Earth-like planets in our galaxy (Howell, 2020). If only one in a thousand of those planets developed an advanced intelligent life, then that would result in 125 million advanced civilizations. Our solar system and planet may be one among millions.

Is there any reason to believe that the development of intelligent life is unique to Earth? The key ingredient for life as we know it is water, and this is recognized by NASA in their definition of an exoplanet's habitable zone: the distance from a star at

which liquid water could exist on an orbiting planet's surface. Is water present on these billions of exoplanets? We've just begun to develop the quality of data to make that assessment on a large scale. We know that the existence of water beyond Earth is much more common than previously thought. Water has been found on 23 moons and planets in our solar system. Jupiter's moons Europa, Enceladus, and Ganymede harbor large quantities of water in frozen oceans (Wenz & Wagh, 2022). Water is plentiful in our solar system, and there is no reason to believe Sol's group of planets are unique. Since water exists in massive quantities in gaseous form in interstellar space (Kotwicki, 1991; van Dishoeck & Blake, 1998), it would be reasonable to expect to find it on planets in the habitable zone of a solar system. NASA's Spitzer Space Telescope has discovered large amounts of simple organic gases, carbon dioxide, and water vapor in a possible planet-forming region around an infant star named AA Tauri and have also found water in the same zone around two other young stars (Carr & Najita, 2008). All five nucleobases that form the building blocks of DNA and RNA—adenine, guanine, cytosine, thymine, and uracil have been found in meteorites (Oba, et al., 2022). The basic ingredients of life are available and the idea that the development of life will lead to intelligence given sufficient time is supported by research in evolutionary biology and astrobiology (Conway, 2003; Krakauer, 2009; Smith & Szathmáry, 1995). All of this points to life being ubiquitous in our galaxy. Until empirical evidence is obtained, we cannot know for certain if intelligent life is ubiquitous on planets with water that are in habitable zones, but an answer of "yes" to the question of whether advanced ET civilizations are prevalent in our galaxy seems worthy of consideration.

Would an ET Civilization Be Aware of Earth's Civilization

A key tenet of the ETH is that an ET civilization would know that there is intelligent life on Earth. Arguments have been made that short of an attempt of direct outward

communication, a civilization will remain hidden in the cosmos (Vaas et al., 1994). Perhaps the best argument indicative of the ease at identifying planet Earth as a site of intelligent life is our own ability to make such a determination using spectroscopic instrumentation to examine the constituent molecules in an exoplanet's atmosphere.

Technosignatures is a 21st century term that refers to technological indicators of advanced civilizations. These include the primary needs of oxygen and water (Goldsmith & Owen, 2001), industrial pollutants (Lin et al., 2014), and artificial light (Wright et al., 2016). Already, we are beginning to develop the ability to spectroscopically measure these signals in an exoplanet's atmosphere. Nine Earth-size planets have been identified where it is believed that the James Webb Space Telescope's (JWST) infrared capabilities should be able to detect some basic atmospheric gases such as oxygen, carbon dioxide, nitrogen, and water (Morley et al., 2017). The Extremely Large Telescope (ELT), under construction in Chile, will complement space-based observations. Its advanced spectrographic instruments are designed to analyze exoplanet atmospheres in detail (Quanz et al., 2015). NASA's Roman Space Telescope, scheduled to launch in 2027, will have a coronagraph to block out the light of an exoplanet's host star. This will be the first step to enable the detection of light emissions from the night side of a planet (Goht, 2024).

Imagine multiple ET civilizations in our galaxy whose astronomical development is several hundred years more advanced than ours. They would have begun observing planets in the habitable zones several hundred years ago. When they first trained their telescopes on Earth, they would have detected nitrogen, oxygen, carbon dioxide, and traces of argon. About two hundred years ago they would have begun to detect increases in our carbon dioxide emissions as well as more complex hydrocarbons in the atmosphere as Earth entered its industrial age. One hundred years ago their telescopes

using coronagraphs to block out the glare of our sun would have detected light from the night-side of our planet as our first cities began the use of incandescent lighting (Levin et al, 2020). Perhaps at this point, some of the ET civilizations would have devoted a telescope to watch our planet constantly. Then, only eighty years ago, they would have detected the first nuclear explosions on our planet while their spectroscopes would have detected isotopes of uranium, plutonium, cesium, strontium, and others in our atmosphere (Prävālie, 2014). As the years passed, they would detect more complex hydrocarbons in the atmosphere as well as a rise in Earth's overall temperature as the percentage of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere increased.

It seems reasonable to answer “yes” that ET civilizations would be aware of the existence of Earth.

ET Motivation to Contact Earth?

Perhaps the most difficult question to answer is related to the motivation or interest of an ET civilization in visiting other star systems. Humans are innately curious but would another species on another planet have that same curiosity? Evidence exists that curiosity and intelligence coincide beyond just humans. Cats and birds have also demonstrated these two characteristics (Ajuwon, 2024; Grand, 1998). Nonetheless, several arguments suggest why extraterrestrial civilizations might avoid contact with Earth. These include the high cost and potential for conflict associated with interstellar travel (Shostak, 2023), the ethical concern of interfering with human development (Ball, 1973), and the risk of biological contamination (Ward & Brownlee, 2000). Proponents of interstellar travel have argued that an ET civilization might be interested in studying another intelligent species for scientific (McCay, 1991), cultural (Cirković, 2004), and even ethical reasons (Freitas, 1980).

Until we contact another ET civilization, it is difficult to answer whether another civilization is motivated to cross vast interstellar distances. Not every ET civilization will be motivated, but it is reasonable to hypothesize based on our limited knowledge that some of the thousands of habitable planets in our galaxy will be sufficiently curious to travel to other worlds.

ETs and Interstellar Travel

The last and most important tenet of the ETH is whether it is feasible to cross interstellar space in any reasonable period of time. This task is so formidable that previous views were that this completely ruled out any type of physical contact between civilizations that existed in our galaxy (Hart, 1975; Hoerner, 1962). This opinion has begun to change.

NASA's Ames Research Center and the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) collaborated on a project to study the requirements to build a spacecraft capable of interstellar travel. This project began with a symposium in Orlando, Florida, in October 2011 that brought together papers from scientists around the nation who were asked to think outside of the box (Schulze-Makuch, 2012). One paper was presented that proposed we use light-weight sails in space to propel small probes to neighboring stars using powerful lasers as the source of propulsion (Lubin, 2016). This concept has resulted in a project called Breakthrough Starshot that was founded by Yuri Milner, Stephen Hawking, and Mark Zuckerberg in 2016 (Parkin, 2018). NASA has endorsed the concept and has a mission concept to launch nano-size spacecraft at 20% the speed of light toward the Alpha Centauri planetary system in 2069 (Millis, 2018). Such a system would be capable of taking and returning digital images of exoplanets as it travelled through the star system.

It is logical to conclude that if we can establish that interstellar travel is feasible for us then other ET civilizations may also have that capability. If we are capable of limited interstellar travel in 50 years, then what would be the capabilities of an ET civilization hundreds of years more advanced than us? Perhaps they could send more than small probes.

Given the hypotheses discussed, advanced ET civilizations likely exist in our galaxy, we would expect they would know that an intelligent civilization exists on Earth, it is difficult to know if they would be motivated or interested in learning more about Earth, and it seems likely that an advanced ET civilization would be able to send probes into our solar system. Therefore, it would be reasonable to entertain the possibility that one or more ET civilizations have either begun observing the Earth from within our solar system or will do so in the near future. An appropriate next step would be to examine the near-Earth environment for signs of ET visitation.

Inductive Analysis: The Case for the Extraterrestrial Hypothesis (ETH)

Many view the inductive determination of the existence of ET as straightforward; we look around and expect to see them if they're here, as was Enrico Fermi's deductive claim (Jones, 1985). We don't expect them to hide from us but to communicate and make their presence known. This lack of immediate ET evidence has led to various explanations: Zoo hypothesis (Ball, 1973), Rare Earth (Ward & Brownlee, 2000), Great Filter (Cirković, 2004; Hanson, 1998), and The Dark Forest (Brin, 1983). Often, we hear the phrase, "Why haven't they landed on the White House lawn?" This expectation is both ethnocentric and anthropocentric. The lack of obvious ET activity along with the view that interstellar travel is next to impossible has led many to the conclusion that ET activity in near Earth space is an unreasonable scientific tenet and is unworthy of pursuit (Menzel & Taves, 1977; Shermer, 1997). This lack of scientific pursuit has

stigmatized the ETH study such that scientists are wary of impacts to their credibility should they pursue the subject (Benford, 2021). NASA's independent study team discussed the scientific barriers that stigma imposes and even discussed their own experience with the issue: "At least one scientist serving on the study team reported receiving negative (hate) mail from colleagues due to their membership." (NASA, 2023). This type of stigma over the decades has led to a failure on the part of the scientific community to inductively examine a valid question based on deductive reasoning (McDonald, 1969). Science should be open and based on the evidence at hand.

Objective and Definition

The objective proposed in this paper is to look for technosignatures of advanced ET intelligence whether in the form of probes, craft, or other evidence, near the Earth. A clear definition of what is needed to meet that objective is required. Once that definition is established then we can measure our effectiveness at identifying ET presence or lack thereof near Earth.

The question of whether we are alone in the universe is a very popular discussion and the public and media want a quick answer without concern for definition. This pressure even affects military and scientific institutions, which have claimed they have found no evidence of extraterrestrial intelligence without defining what type of evidence is required (NASA, 2023; ODNI, 2024).

One reasonable definition for the presence of ET craft is evidence of extremely high acceleration as this would likely be necessary for any interstellar spacecraft. A craft accelerating at 100 g would reach 10% of the speed of light in 8.5 hrs, 30% of the speed of light in just more than a day and would reach Proxima Centauri in a month and a half (Knuth et al., 2019). This type of acceleration is a hallmark of interstellar travel and is

also well beyond current human capabilities (Anderson, 2007; Knuth et al., 2019). Measuring this level of acceleration will require very accurate scientific instrumentation and extensive characterization of the equipment capabilities. (Watters et al., 2023). Other characteristics besides extreme acceleration could be identified as a hallmark of a non-terrestrial craft such as lack of interaction with the atmosphere while moving at high speed. These definitions of technosignatures in the near-Earth realm need to be established and agreed upon by the scientific community before claims can be made as to whether there is or is not evidence of ET activity in our atmosphere or in near-Earth space.

Information from past reports and their analysis of UAP/UFO should be studied in order to provide a baseline of the type of equipment needed as well as the necessary precision and accuracy of the measuring equipment (Watters et al., 2023).

Currently Available Data

There is an anthropocentric tendency with humans to think of humanity discovering ET rather than ET discovering humanity. A logical conclusion of such a thought would be that the more advanced civilization will first discover the less advanced civilization. This concept has only been lightly mentioned in the literature (Ball, 1973) while the concept of when will we discover ET signatures is the prevailing mode of thought. Only in science fiction does ET come to us first. This innate tendency may cause us to be slow at considering other realities.

It has been hypothesized that some of the unknown objects that have been reported in Earth's atmosphere may be of ET origin (Hynek, 1972; Lubin, 2016; Powell, 2024; Sachdeva, 2024). These unknown objects have been referred to by a variety of names including foo fighters, flying saucers, unidentified flying objects (UFOs), and more recently, unknown anomalous phenomena (UAP), a term which came into use in 2020

(Powell, 2024). Although unknown objects in our skies have been reported on occasion for hundreds of years (Hynek, 1972) the modern era that consists of large numbers of reports and many by qualified observers such as pilots, law enforcement, and even astronomers, began in 1942 (Chester, 2007). A graph that illustrates this paradigm change based on frequency of reports of unknown aerial objects is provided in Figure 1 at the end of this paper (Powell, 2024). There have been over 100,000 reports of unknown objects during this time (Posard et al., 2023). The vast majority (90%+) of these reports are misidentified objects (Hendry, 1979; USAF, 1992.)

Among these reports are some which are indicative of oddly shaped objects that operate with unusual kinematics such as wide speed variations, sudden changes of direction, and high acceleration (Powell et al., 2023; Swords et al., 2012). Extreme acceleration is one of the unique kinematics displayed by these objects. There are multiple witness reports of craft at a close range that accelerate and recede from view within one to two seconds (Powell, 2024) and that demonstrate what appears to be instantaneous acceleration to the observer (Greenwood & Davidson-Arnott, 2020). Visual observation of extreme acceleration can be calculated using trigonometry and the angular size of the object, its approximate size, the distance required for the angular size to decrease below the human eyesight threshold, and the resulting acceleration required to cover that distance in one to two seconds (Knuth et al., 2019; Powell et al., 2019). One of the most famous of these incidents occurred in 2004 off the coast of southern California and involved the USS *Nimitz*, the USS *Princeton*, and two F-18 Super Hornets (Powell et al., 2019). There are also incidents that involved radar detection and high accelerations (Oberth, 1954; Poher, 2005; Powell et al., 2019; Sagan & Page, 1972).

In addition to the incident just mentioned involving the USS *Nimitz*, there are dozens of reports made by multiple credible witnesses, sometimes with supporting evidence, that appear to the witnesses to be a technologically advanced craft that are not of Earthly origin. Many of these have been well investigated with extensive reports regarding the events:

- (1) McMinnville, Oregon; May 11, 1950; visual sighting and photos of a disk (Maccabee, 1976).
- (2) Gulf Coast U.S.; July 17, 1957; RB-47 Air Force trailed for several hours, visual sighting and radar (McDonald, 1970; USAF, 1957a).
- (3) Levelland, Texas; November 2-3, 1957; autos stalled by egg-shaped object (Hynek, 1972; USAF, 1957b).
- (4) Damon, Texas; September 3, 1965; law enforcement witnesses of large triangle (USAF, 1965).
- (5) Redlands, California; February 4, 1968; visual sighting and audio recording (Krupke, 2016).
- (6) Minot AFB, North Dakota; October 24, 1968; radar and visual sighting by multiple military soldiers and pilots; intrusion at a nuclear facility; (Poher, 2005; USAF, 1968).
- (7) Delphos, Kansas; November 2, 1971; visual sighting of a dome-shaped object and possible trace evidence in the soil (Faruk, 2021; Swords, 1991).
- (8) Mansfield, Ohio; October 18, 1973; visual sighting of a cigar-shaped object by pilots in a helicopter and civilians on the ground (Zeidman, 1979).
- (9) Loring AFB, Maine; October 27-28, 1975; radar and visual sighting by multiple military personnel of a football-shaped object; intrusion at a nuclear facility (Fawcett & Greenwood, 1984; Tingley, 2020).

- (10) Tehran, Iran; September 19, 1976; radar, visual sighting, and engagement by military pilots (Maccabee, 2006; NSA, 1976).
- (11) Belgium; November 29, 1989; radar and visual sightings of triangles by military, civilians, and law enforcement (Meessen, 2011; Wilfried, 2008).
- (12) Chicago, O'Hare; November 7, 2006; visual sightings by pilots and civilians of a disk (Haines et al., 2006).
- (13) Stephenville, Texas; January 8, 2008; radar and visual sightings by civilians and law enforcement (Powell & Schulze, 2008).
- (14) Aguadilla, Puerto Rico; April 25, 2013; visual sightings by pilots and IR video (Powell et al., 2015).
- (15) Atlantic Ocean off Florida; January 2015; visual sightings by pilots and IR video (Peings & von Rennenkampff, 2023).

It cannot be proven that these are ET craft, only that the characteristics reported seem to indicate that they are not of human origin. Assumptions can be made to provide explanations for individual incidents such as possible equipment error or human perception error. Individually, these assumptions seem reasonable but as the number of incidents requiring independent assumptions for explanations increases and/or the number of assumptions required to explain an individual event increases, the resultant likelihood of all those independent assumptions being valid decreases (Jeffreys, 1998). A final resolution to the question of these anomalous observations will require several high-precision scientific measurements of craft displaying technosignatures of an advanced technology to resolve this argument.

Data Collection and Communication Program

Investigations and analysis of UAP/UFO reports since the second World War have been dominated by mostly non-scientists in the military in the United States and except for

France, in all other major nations (Swords et al., 2012). Eighty years of off-and-on military investigations in the U.S. have led to no solid conclusions. The military's responsibility is national security and consequentially involves secrecy and withholding of information even between the various military service and three letter agencies (Swords et al.,2012). We must move away from a military-based study of the phenomenon to a science-based study. The former is controlled by secrecy while the latter depends on openness and collaboration.

A network of automated data collection camera systems should be established to collect data on unknown objects transversing Earth's atmosphere as well as moving through near-Earth space. This can be done with ground-based systems as well as satellite systems. Civilian scientists on private shoestring budgets have begun to develop and characterize these systems (Vodopivec & Kayal, 2018; Watters et al., 2023). These systems should be capable of measuring the technosignatures that are defined to indicate the presence of an ET craft.

Congress must take the initiative to provide funding to develop these systems by academia and the scientific community. Congress could provide the funding through the National Science Foundation (NSF) with guidance from NASA or another appropriate agency. Congress should provide specific directives to NSF, through the appropriations process, so that funds are directed specifically to the study of UAP/UFO and the development of a network of automated monitoring stations. There have been no studies that identify the costs to properly study UAP/UFO, but it would likely be hundreds of millions of dollars.

In addition to obtaining scientific data on technosignatures in near-Earth space, there should also be an attempt to communicate with any unknown objects that are detected. Communication protocols should first be established through an international body

(Michaud, 2015). Communication signals could be sent across multiple EM frequencies . Given the apparent attraction of UAP to nuclear facilities (Porritt et al., 2023), conducting these communication attempts in close proximity to such sites could enhance the possibility of success.

Conclusion

Deductive reasoning can bring us to the conclusion that there is a reasonable possibility that there should be ET visiting Earth. Meanwhile, inductive reasoning—based on the study of UFO/UAP sightings reported since 1942—leads some to consider whether these sightings indicate extraterrestrial presence. Others of us wonder why we have not been contacted over the last 80 years if some of these sighting reports are ET. Could this view reflect our anthropocentric perspective, assuming that if we have not been contacted, then extraterrestrial life must not be present?

One could argue that a paradigm change began in 1992 with the discovery of the first exoplanets, followed by the identification of thousands more over the last 32 years. This new information has created a new paradigm that tells us that life in the cosmos is likely common. Naturally, this leads to speculation about whether the unidentified objects observed in our skies could be of extraterrestrial origin. This shift in thinking is already evident in the growing scientific interest in studying UAP. The new generation of today's scientists have known about exoplanets since they were in grade school.

It will be this new generation of scientists who will address Dr. James McDonald's plea made in 1969 before the Aeronautics and Space Institute Symposium: "Science in Default: Twenty-Two Years of Inadequate UFO Investigations." (McDonald, 1969, p.1) Someday the time will come when we make first contact with another intelligence. We must start now to develop clear definitions of near-Earth technosignatures, communication protocols, and the responsible and ethical sharing of knowledge gained

from such contact. Furthermore, we must consider who should represent humanity in such a momentous event. Should it be a nation-state's military organization or an entity that speaks for all of humanity? This is a critical question with far-reaching implications for the future of our species.

Figure 1 UFO sighting reports obtained from the following combined databases: Project Blue Book, MUFON, NICAP, CUFOS, GEIPAN, Project 1947, and the International Catalogue of UFO Reports. Source: (Powell, 2024)

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